

CERTIFICATE

OF PUBLICATION

This certificate is proudly presented to

Dr. Vandana Pandey

In recognition for the paper publication under

Shodh Patra Journal

with the article title:

Smartphone Addiction and Its Impact on the Wellbeing of School Students: A Comprehensive Review

Vol. 3 No. 1 (YEAR 2026): SHODH PATRA ISSN: 3048-7196
Open Access Journal with Impact Score of 6.3 by UJIF

May - 2026

Date

Editor
PARHLAD